

APPENDIX - Survey Questionnaire

General View of the Research

My name is Ivaldir H. de Farias Júnior, and I am a Doctorate candidate in Computer Science in the Center of Informatics (Centro de Informática – Cin) of the Federal University of Pernambuco – (Universidade Federal de Pernambuco – UFPE), under the guidance of the PhD. Professor Hermano Perrelli de Moura and the PhD. Professor Sabrina Marczak, from the PUCRS. First of all, I would like to thank you by volunteering to answer this research. Your feedback is extremely valuable to the conclusion of this work. The following questionnaire finishes one more evaluation step of this Doctorate Work, which have as basis the elaboration of a maturity model for communication in Distributed Software Development (DSD).

The maturity model for communication in distributed software development called C2M (Communication Maturity Model) contains 4 maturity levels and 15 communication factors distributed in the referred levels. This research aims to evaluate the organization and objective of the maturity levels of the C2M model, the distribution of the factors in the maturity levels, the definition of every factor and their respective practices.

15 minutes are necessary for the reading of the documents and 35 minutes more, in average, to answer the questionnaire completely. We kindly ask you to COMPLETELY answer it. In contrary, we will need to discard it, once the incomplete questionnaires will not be considered valid to our research. Your personal data will be kept in confidence, and your contributions will be used only for academic purposes.

Regards,

Ivaldir H. de Farias Júnior

About you and your Experience

1. What is your name?
2. What is your e-mail?
3. How old are you?
4. What Is your gender?
 - () Female
 - () Male
5. In which city do you live?
6. In which state do you live?
7. What is your scholarship?

() Graduation

() Specialization

() Master

() Doctorate

() Post-Doctorate

Other (specify)

8. What is your formation area?

() Computing/Informatics

() Management

() Communication

Other (Specify)

9. What position do you actually hold?

() Project Manager

() Technical Leader

() Software Developer

() Software Tester

() Requirements analyst

() Student

Researcher (professor)

Other

Others (Specify)

10. What type of experience do you have in Distributed Software Development (DSD)

Software Industry

Academy

Both

11. How long is your DSD experience?

12. What is the name of the organization that you actually work in?

13. What is the size of the organization that you actually work in?

Micro – Up to 9 employees

Small – from 10 to 49 employees

Medium – from 50 to 99 employees

Large – more than 100 employees

I am Student

14. The organization you actually work in is certified in quality models?

The company does not have certification

CMMI

ISO

MPS.BR

MPT.BR

Other

Other (specify)

Assessment of the C2M – Communication Maturity Model

Next we present the maturity levels of the C2M and their objectives. Consider them when answering the following questions.

LEVEL	OBJECTIVE
Level 1 – Casual	The initial level of every organization, without the practices defined. This means that each organization execute the communication activities in an ad-hoc form.
Level 2 – Partially managed	The organization processes start to change, including basic communication activities. These activities mainly include aspects of communication planning.
Level 3 – Managed	The team members work in a self-organized and simultaneous way to maintain an effective communication and attend the Project objectives. The distributed teams understand the process of the work they will perform, understand their objectives, are conscious of the necessary steps to reach these objectives and have the necessary knowledge to execute the tasks.
Level 4 – Reflexive	It Predicts a constant communication and motivation to improve the performance of every team, once the standards (for example, organizational processes, reports, plans and communication media, etc.) are created and institutionalized organizationally.

15. In your opinion, the number of levels of the C2M model is adequate to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?
- () Yes, no changes are required.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be included.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be excluded.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be grouped.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be updated.
16. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update?
17. In your opinion, the objective of every level of the C2M model is adequate to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- () Yes, no changes are required.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be included.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be excluded.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be grouped.
- () No, one or more maturity levels must be updated.

18. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update?

Next, are presented the factors of every maturity level, and their objectives. Consider them to answer the following questions.

Level	Factors	Objective of the factor
2	Managing cultural differences	The objective of this factor is to understand the difficulties existing due to cultural differences and prepare the teams to act in DSD projects knowing and respecting these differences.
	Communication support tools	The objective of this factor is to make an adequate use of the existing tools, considering the scenery of distribution of the teams.
	IT infrastructure	The objective of this factor is to plan the infrastructure which will be made available to the distributed teams.
	Managing the geographic distance	The objective of this factor is to improve the levels of perception of physical distance existing between the teams.
	Managing the time distance	The objective of this factor is to understand and improve the levels of perception of the time distance.
	Stakeholder management	The objective of this factor is to perform the planning and management of the stakeholders, considering the profile and proficiency required for the Project.
	Communication Planning	The objective of this factor is to plan the communication from the beginning to the end of the Project.
	Risk Management	The objective of this factor is to identify, analyze, treat and monitor the risks.
	Communication policies and standards	The objective of this factor is to establish and maintain communication policies and standards that add value to the Project.
	Requirements elicitation and specification	The objective of this factor is to provide a better understanding in the elicitation and specification of the requirements, seeking to improve the spoken and written communication of the artifacts from this activity.

Level	Factors	Objective of the factor
3	Managing cultural differences	The objective of this factor is to understand the difficulties existing due to cultural differences and prepare the teams to act in DSD projects knowing and respecting these differences.
	Communication support tools	The objective of this factor is to make an adequate use of the existing tools, considering the scenery of distribution of the teams.
	IT infrastructure	The objective of this factor is to plan the infrastructure which will be made available to the distributed teams.

	Managing the geographic distance	The objective of this factor is to improve the levels of perception of physical distance existing between the teams.
	Managing the time distance	The objective of this factor is to understand and improve the levels of perception of the time distance.
	Stakeholder management	The objective of this factor is to perform the planning and management of the stakeholders, considering the profile and proficiency required for the Project.
	Communication Planning	The objective of this factor is to plan the communication from the beginning to the end of the Project.
	Risk management	The objective of this factor is to identify, analyze, treat and monitor the risks.
	Communication policies and standards	The objective of this factor is to establish and maintain communication policies and standards that add value to the project.
	Requirements elicitation and specification	The objective of this factor is to provide a better understanding in the elicitation and specification of the requirements, seeking to improve the spoken and written communication of the artifacts from this activity.
	Trust acquiring	The objective of this factor is to solve or minimize the difficulties from the absence of trust between the teams.
	Communication Training	The objective of this factor is to develop abilities and knowledge to permit the members of the project perform effectively their roles.
	Configuration Management	The objective of this factor is to establish and maintain the integrity of the artifacts generated (products of the work) along the project, as well as, ease the communication of the alteration in documents and codes which suffered any change.

Level	Factors	Objective of the factor
4	Continuous improvement of the communication	The objective of this factor is to promote continuously the maintaining and improvement of the communication in the organization.
	Monitoring, measurement and analysis	The objective of this factor is to provide subsidies to develop and maintain a capacity for monitor, measure and analyze, with the purpose of providing information to the high management.
	Stakeholder management	The objective of this factor is to perform the planning and management of the stakeholders, considering the profile and proficiency required for the Project.
	Communication Training	The objective of this factor is to develop abilities and knowledge to permit the members of the project perform effectively their roles.

19. In your opinion, the Level 1 (casual) of the C2M model is really needed?
Remember that this level actually is only an initial level, without associated maturity factors.

() Yes

() No

() Maybe

20. In case of answering “Yes” to the previous question, point some factors that should be associated to the Level 1 Casual.

21. In your opinion, the maturity factors contained in the levels 2, 3 or 4 of the C2M Model are adequately distributed for the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be included.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be excluded.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be grouped.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be updated.

22. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update?

23. In your opinion, the maturity factors contained in the levels 2, 3 or 4 of the C2M Model are adequately described?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be moved.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be excluded.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be grouped.
- No, one or more maturity factors must be updated.

24. What are your suggestions in case of the need for move or update?

25. The practices of the factors of the level 2 are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more practices must be included.
- No, one or more practices must be excluded.

0 No, one or more practices must be grouped.

0 No, one or more practices must be updated.

26. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update the practices contained in the Level 2 – partially managed?

Next are presented the practices contained in the C2M maturity factors. Consider them when answering the next questions.

Maturity Level	Communication maturity Factor	Communication Practices
2	Managing cultural differences	Establish policies for the recruitment and selection of new talents for the project; Identify and Institutionalize the cultural context of every team in the project;
	Communication support tools	Adopt synchronous and/or asynchronous communication tools on demand; Adopt collaboration tools;
	IT infrastructure	Define the infrastructure considering the dispersion level of the teams; Monitor periodically the IT infrastructure;
	Managing the geographic distance	Plan face-to-face meetings; Plan and perform the frequent communication;
	Managing the time distance	Plan and manage the synchronization of the team time shifts; Plan and perform the continuity of the tasks (handoffs passage);
	Stakeholder management	Identify the stakeholders; Define roles and responsibilities
	Communication Planning	Establish a communication strategy; Establish mechanisms to confirm the understanding of the activities; Establish a default language for the project; Establish a communication plan; Establish the stakeholder commitment with the communication planning; Define a communication focal point (interlocutor comunicacional); Manage the data (artifacts) of the project;
	Risk Management	Identify communication risks Assess, categorize and prioritize communication risks Identify the relevant stakeholders associated to each risk;
	Communication policies and standards	Establish a communication policy;
Requirements elicitation and specification	Obtain the confirmation of the requirement understanding by the team members; Manage the requirement changes;	

Maturity Level	Communication maturity Factor	Communication Practices
3	Managing cultural differences	Establish a basis of cultural knowledge; Standardize jargons and vocabulary of the Project; Plan initiatives to mitigate occurrences caused by the cultural differences;
	Communication support tools	Adopt face-to-face communication tools;
	Trust acquiring	Establish integration strategies between the stakeholders; Interchange of members between the disperse Project teams of the Project; Encourage the collaboration and cooperation between the teams
	Infrastructure	Maintain backup of the IT infrastructure;
	Managing the geographic distance	Establish a discussion forum in the project; Plan initiatives to mitigate the occurrences caused by the geographical distance;
	Managing the time distance	Plan and manage the follow-the-sun strategy (almost continuous Development); Plan initiatives to mitigate occurrences caused by the time distance;
	Stakeholder Management	Plan the management of the stakeholders;
	Communication Planning	Plan and manage the meetings; Gather, document and communicate the lessons learned;
	Risk Management	Elaborate Plans of risk mitigation;
	Communication policies and standards	Establish standards for documentation and communication;
	Communication training	Plan trainings in communication; Provide trainings in communication; Register trainings in communication;
	Configuration management	Establish the version and modification control; Establish access control to the configuration items; Establish a configuration plan to the whole Project;
Requirements elicitation and specification	Maintain the requirement traceability;	

Maturity Level	Communication maturity Factor	Communication Practices
4	Stakeholder Management	Monitor and assess the relationship between the stakeholders;
	Continuous improvement of the communication	Perform systematically the analysis of the data collected in the Project; Provide orientation for the use of the data; Research, assess and monitor new communication processes, methods and tools to apply in the organization; Establish, monitor and maintain the strategic action plan for the improvement of the organization's communication;
	Communication Training	Assess the benefits of the communication training;

	Monitoring, measurement and analysis	Establish the objective of the measurement for communication; Establish gathering, storage and analysis procedures for the communication data; Communicate the results of the measurement;
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27. The practices of the factors of the level 3 are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more practices must be included.
- No, one or more practices must be excluded.
- No, one or more practices must be grouped.
- No, one or more practices must be updated.

28. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update the practices contained in the Level 3 – managed?

29. The practices of the factors of the level 3 – managed are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more practices must be included.
- No, one or more practices must be excluded.
- No, one or more practices must be grouped.
- No, one or more practices must be updated.

30. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update the practices contained in the Level 3 – managed?

31. The practices of the factors of the level 4 - Reflexive are described in an adequate way to the assessment of the communication maturity in DSD?

- Yes, no changes are required.
- No, one or more practices must be included.
- No, one or more practices must be excluded.

No, one or more practices must be grouped.

No, one or more practices must be updated.

32. What are your suggestions in case of the need for inclusion, exclusion, grouping or update the practices contained in the Level 4 - reflexive?

33. How do you evaluate the need for a maturity model which helps the organizations that work with DSD to assess the communication in their projects

Unnecessary

Few necessary

Necessary

Very necessary

Extremely necessary

34. How do you evaluate the ease of implementation of the C2M maturity model for the communication in the DSD context:

Very simple to implement

Simple to implement

Regular

Moderately complex to implement

Very complex to implement

35. If you wish, justify the answer of the previous question.

36. Would you adopt this model in a DSD Project?

Yes

No

Maybe

37. If you wish, justify the answer of the previous question.

38. In your opinion, what benefit this communication maturity model brings to the companies that adopt DSD projects?